

HOW PROFESSIONALS CAN BENEFIT FROM AINO AID™ - SERVICE?

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We Encourage

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VIOLENCE HAS ALWAYS SERIOUS CONSEQUENCES

A large portion of people have experienced intimate partner violence at some point in their lives, even if they may not recognise it. Violence may have occurred in their childhood family, between parents or siblings or as part of their upbringing. They may have also encountered violence in a dating or friendship relationship and later in life within a partnership or still within their own family. Even one's own child can behave violently toward a parent.

Violence always has serious consequences. Experiencing emotional abuse is known to lead to depression or anxiety disorders. Living amidst violence is an enormous stressor that can result in stress disorders, panic, and compulsive behaviours. PTSD is also often triggered by experiences of violence. Violence can be challenging to recognise—it encompasses much more than physical harm, often beginning subtly becoming normalised over time, with the person affected adapting to the circumstances.

For these reasons, those who experience violence often seek help for symptoms like depression, anxiety, panic disorder, social anxiety, obsessive-compulsive disorder, stress, or a vague sense of unease and questioning what might be wrong. It is thus crucial for therapists to recognise the underlying causes of these symptoms.

It is essential for those who experience violence to feel safe, understood, and heard. Recovery is challenging if the home environment does not change. The perpetrator of violence also needs support and therapy, and sometimes, the reason for seeking therapy is a fear of harming loved ones. Many perpetrators of violence have a history of experiencing violence themselves.

AinoAid™ for professionals

If a professional working in violence prevention does not have specialised expertise in violence, they can utilise AinoAid™.

AinoAid™ is designed to support professionals as well. It assists in recognising signs of violence, allowing users to ask direct questions in the chat or access information on forms, dynamics, and cycles of violence through AinoAid™'s knowledge base. Professionals can anonymously describe a client's situation in the chat and receive guidance on how to proceed and what to consider.

For professionals, it may sometimes be unclear how to act practically if a client requires safety measures, a safety plan, or if there are children in the family. AinoAid™ provides clear instructions on when to make a child protection report, notify the police, or guide the client to safety and where to refer them.

A client experiencing violence in a close relationship is in an extremely stressful life situation and needs support beyond scheduled services. In such cases, it is beneficial to provide them with access to AinoAid™ for use at any time. AinoAid™ is available 24/7, allowing the client to share their feelings or describe events in the chat. They also receive direct guidance from AinoAid™ itself. Situations in relationships involving violence can escalate quickly and unexpectedly, and it may not always be possible to anticipate every development. AinoAid™ also helps clients better articulate their experiences to a professional, making its use mutually beneficial.

Clients are sometimes concerned with various practical matters that professionals do not necessarily need to address if these do not directly fall within their role. Such concerns might include criminal and legal processes, the rights of those affected by violence, issues related to child custody, support, visitation, housing, financial concerns, therapy, and so on. For these types of questions, clients can access comprehensive information from AinoAid™, freeing up appointments from being focused on practical matters. AinoAid™ also provides contact details and guidance on topics such as finding safety, what that entails, and what to expect in a shelter, as clients often have questions about these aspects in advance.

Finding the right professional can be challenging, especially one with understanding and expertise in domestic violence. Through AinoAid™, providers specialising in domestic violence support, such as therapists, can showcase their services, making it easier for clients to find the support they need.

BENEFITS FOR PROFESSIONALS

1 Helps to

- identify domestic violence as a possible underlying factor in the client's symptoms
- validate the client's experience
- provide accurate information to the client about domestic violence
- assess the need for safety measures
- evaluate the required actions that the professional is obligated to take
- guide the client towards appropriate services
- assist the client in finding the right words to describe their situation/experiences
- assess, together with the client, the need for ongoing therapy

2 Guides

- initiating and discussing the topic with the client
- allows the professional to ask AinoAid™ directly about the client's situation and receive guidance on how to proceed
- can be provided for the client's use between, for example, therapy sessions

3 Provides

- additional information on the topic for professionals
- relevant links and contact details
- answers to questions commonly asked by clients experiencing violence

Guidance for using AinoAid™

1 Utilise the knowledge base

- Forms of violence
- The dynamics and cycle of violence
- Recognising and addressing violence

Guidance and processes

on:

- Choosing the right service
- Checklists
- Criminal process
- Court proceedings
- Leaving for safety
- Contact details

2 Ask the bot for lists, e.g.

I suspect that my client is experiencing violence.

- Create a list of probing questions that could help me bring up my concerns.
- List the things that my client needs to consider in their safety plan.

3 Ask the bot for advice, e.g.

- I would like to validate my client's experiences. How can I do that most effectively?
- I need to reach out to a client whom I am concerned about. Could you help me write a message in which I can politely express my concerns?

Collaboration is the key to making an impact!

- **Co-development and projects:** We collaborate to develop tailored solutions and train different professional groups.
- **Events:** We organise events and webinars and participate in various occasions together.
- **Communication:** We gladly write guest blogs, engage in co-marketing, and offer our networks and platforms as channels to raise awareness.

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